

Public Preferences for Reallocating Aid in the Presence of Alternative Donors

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Abstract: Research has shown that people support foreign aid more when reminded of its strategic uses or when cued to think about international competition. Additional strategic considerations might affect evaluations of foreign aid. We examine whether citizens in aid-giving countries distinguish across different types of substituting donors, explore whether attitudes regarding aid are underpinned by countries' relative power positions, and investigate citizens' support for reallocating aid from one set of recipient countries to another. We test the impact of these strategic considerations using parallel online survey experiments conducted on representative samples from Japan and the United States. In Japan, we find that reference to either an adversary or an ally as a substitute donor reduces support for aid reallocation. Mediation analysis confirms that respondents' attitudes are driven by national interest considerations. In the United States, respondents perceive that aid substitution by an adversary—but not an ally—will negatively impact national interests, but these concerns are not sufficient to change opinions regarding aid reallocation. We attribute these findings to donor publics' different understandings of their country's relative position in the international system and the differing roles of foreign aid in pursuing national objectives.

Keywords: foreign aid, international competition, rivalry, public opinion, survey experiment

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“The compulsion of substituting for the traditional businesslike transmission of bribes the pretense and elaborate machinery of foreign aid for economic development results from a climate of opinion which accepts as universally valid the proposition that the highly developed industrial nations have an obligation to transfer money and services to underdeveloped nations for the purpose of economic development” (Morgenthau 1962, 302).

As Morgenthau described in his influential article, the modern foreign aid infrastructure is a Cold War creation within which the transfer of resources motivated by political, commercial, and other self-interested purposes is often disguised in altruistic discourse about development, poverty alleviation, and humanitarian relief. The taxpaying citizens in donor countries, who ultimately fund foreign aid programs, are therefore exposed to competing ideas about what foreign aid is for and what it is doing. On the one hand, they are periodically reminded of their moral obligations to assist people in need and contribute to economic development in poor countries. On the other hand, they hear politicians discuss foreign aid as a tool for pursuing national security, commercial access, and international status.

The scholarly literature generally confirms that citizens in donor countries draw on both strategic and humanitarian considerations to form their judgments regarding whether certain recipient countries are appropriate targets for foreign aid. Some studies show that arguments about the economic benefits and national security implications of aid are persuasive, while others find that donor publics tend to be averse to providing aid to countries engaged in behavior deemed morally reprehensible (Heinrich, Kobayashi, and Long 2018; Heinrich and Kobayashi 2020; Kohno et al. 2021; Wood, Hoy, and Pryke 2021; Wood and Hoy 2022; Chung, Pechenkina, and Skinner 2023; Strange 2023). Most recently, in line with research that emphasizes strategic considerations, a set of studies has focused on the changing structure of the international system and how increasing competition among donors affects public evaluations of aid policies (Kohno et al. 2021; Wood, Hoy, and Pryke 2021; Chung, Pechenkina, and Skinner 2023).

We build on this literature in three ways with new survey experiments. First, we examine whether citizens in aid-giving countries distinguish across different types of competing donors. When examining public responses to aid competition, previous work has assumed that alternative donors will be adversaries. Yet, it is unlikely that all donors would be viewed in the same light. We thus extend previous work to consider citizens’ responses to the prospect of allies serving as substitute aid donors. Second, we take seriously the possibility that public attitudes regarding aid are underpinned by countries’ relative power positions in the international system generally and in the dyadic relationship of an actual alliance in particular. We conduct survey experiments in two countries, the United States and

Japan. The United States, as a global superpower, can utilize military, intelligence, and other means to exercise its influence externally; Japan, while it is a powerful country on many dimensions, places far greater weight on foreign aid as a policy tool because of constitutional constraints on the use of military force. Third, we investigate, as an outcome variable, citizens' support for reallocating aid from one set of recipient countries to another, rather than citizens' preferences for increasing or decreasing aid in general. Assessing how to allocate aid across countries or regions is more likely to elicit another strategic consideration—the relative importance to donor publics of some aid recipients over others—than simply considering the size of the aid budget. Examining support for aid reallocation, as we do in our surveys, also has a methodological advantage over simply asking about preferences regarding aid levels: by holding the budget constant, we minimize the influence of heterogeneity in individuals' priors regarding the size of the aid budget and the allocation of government spending. In this way, we are better able to isolate responses to information regarding alternative donors.

In running our public opinion experiments, we made efforts to approximate the reality of the contemporary international situations surrounding the two donor countries.¹ Thus, instead of referring to substitute donors as simply an abstract adversary or ally, we use concrete country names. In both Japan and the United States, China is treated as the hypothetical adversarial donor likely to step in, should Japan/the United States withdraw their aid from a particular region of the world. In the Japan survey, the United States is treated as the hypothetical ally whose aid might substitute for Japanese aid, while in the U.S. survey, the United Kingdom and Japan are treated as the allies. Also, for the sake of increasing naturalism, we use concrete names of geographical regions to and from which aid reallocations are to take place. For Japanese respondents, we introduce two potential reallocation scenarios: (1) aid currently going to Africa reallocated to Southeast Asia and, conversely, (2) aid currently going to Southeast Asia reallocated to Africa. In the U.S. survey, we use Africa, Latin America, and Southeast Asia as relevant world regions, and the exhaustive combination of the three regions makes for six hypothetical aid reallocation situations.

Our analysis proceeds in two stages. First, we conduct standard regression analyses to estimate the treatment effects of our main experimental stimuli. Second, we conduct mediation analyses to explore mechanisms linking the treatments and respondents' preferences regarding aid reallocation, by utilizing a set of questions placed prior to the outcome question: they ask how reallocation may affect the respondent country's (1) economic interests, (2) national security interests, and (3) international reputation, and (4) the current recipient region's development prospects.

Our results indicate that respondents in Japan are consistently more sensitive to strategic aspects of the aid-giving environment than respondents in the United States. In Japan, we find that *any* mention of aid substitution by another donor, whether an adversary (China) or an ally (United States), decreases respondents' support for aid reallocation. Furthermore, mediation analysis confirms that their consistently negative attitude changes are driven by national interest considerations: the treatment effects are mediated through mechanisms related to respondents' perceptions of Japan's own economic interest, national security, and international reputation, but not through a mechanism related to the development prospects of the recipient regions. By contrast, our results from the U.S. survey show that average treatment effects are statistically insignificant regardless of whether U.S. aid is expected to be replaced by an adversary (China) or an ally (either the United Kingdom or Japan). We find these null results both in the analysis of data pooled across reallocation scenarios and in the analyses conducted separately for the six region-specific scenarios. This is not to say, however, that Americans are entirely insensitive to geostrategic context. Although they are indifferent to aid substitution by either an adversary or an ally, their attitudes toward aid reallocation vary with their subjective assessment of the importance of maintaining relations with the regions from or to which aid might be reallocated. Moreover, according to the mediation analysis, when the alternative donor is China—but not when it is the United Kingdom or Japan—Americans perceive that the aid substitution will negatively impact U.S. economic interests, national security, and international reputation, although not sufficiently to change opinions on aid reallocation.

Support for Foreign Aid as a Strategic Tool

Although support for foreign aid features in some classic studies of public opinion (e.g., Page and Shapiro 1992), until recently, there had been relatively little research seeking to understand the determinants of mass public opinion about foreign aid. Initially, much attention was paid to various individual-level correlates of support for foreign aid. In a seminal article, Paxton and Knack (2012) report that wealthier respondents, women, more religious individuals, those with left-leaning ideologies, those with greater awareness of international affairs, and those with higher levels of social trust are more supportive of foreign aid. Other studies, such as vanHeerde and Hudson (2010) and Henson and Lindstrom (2013), find that individuals who perceive a moral duty to provide aid are more likely to support foreign aid. Heinrich, Kobayashi, and Bryant (2016) show that prevailing economic conditions also influence attitudes toward aid, with individuals affected by economic downturns being less supportive of foreign aid. Scotto et al. (2017) demonstrate that support for foreign aid increases with

better information about a country's actual aid expenditures, but that, even after correcting misperceptions, significant opposition to aid remains.

Citizens' perceptions of the effectiveness and efficacy of aid have also been an important theme in the literature. For example, support for aid has been found to be lower among people who think that aid is generally wasted (Henson and Lindstrom 2013; see also Heinrich and Kobayashi 2020) or who think that corruption is a significant problem in aid-receiving countries (Bauhr, Charron, and Nasiritousi 2013). Scholars also have found that the public does not support aid flows to regimes that violate human rights (Allendoerfer 2017; Dasandi et al. 2022).

Some studies have explicitly examined the extent to which primes about the strategic use of aid generate public support for aid. Empirical findings from these studies are mixed. On the one hand, Hurst, Tidwell, and Hawkins (2017) report that information about aid's role in promoting a donor's own interests has little effect on people, whereas arguments about recipient need and the low costs of aid have substantially larger effects. Wood and Hoy (2022), on the other hand, find that the argument that aid serves the national interest has a somewhat larger effect on people's willingness to support aid than an argument about aid helping poor countries. Dietrich, Hyde, and Winters (2019) present evidence that watching a video describing the use of aid branding leads people to say that the donor does a good job of ensuring that aid is well spent, although it does not increase support for aid overall. Allendoerfer (2017) finds little evidence that the strategic importance of a recipient country moderates the effect of human rights violations on people's willingness to support aid flows to that particular regime, while Heinrich, Kobayashi, and Long (2018) find that either security or economic interests lead people to relax their negative attitudes surrounding giving foreign aid to a human-rights-abusing regime. Strange (2023) shows that the U.S. public—and the Chinese public to a lesser extent—use information about types of foreign aid projects to make subtle inferences about the influence a donor government will have over a recipient government.

Most recently, a set of studies has focused on whether the presence of a competing donor inspires public enthusiasm for foreign aid. Wood, Hoy, and Pryke (2021) find that, in Australia and New Zealand, survey respondents' opposition to aid decreases when they receive information about Chinese aid giving in the Pacific; indeed they become more interested in specifically channeling aid to that region. Surprisingly, however, the exposure to information about Chinese aid reduces respondents' perceptions that aid should be used to pursue national interests. Kohno et al. (2021) show that support for cancelling aid in the wake of human rights violations (i.e., support for employing aid sanctions) drops among the Japanese public if they receive information about a competing donor—again China—waiting

in the wings; their mediation analysis suggests that this change in the outcome variable originates most prominently in concerns that cancelling aid will affect Japan's security. Chung, Pechenkina, and Skinner (2023) show that a prime about Chinese COVID assistance to Latin America increases American support for U.S. spending on COVID assistance to Latin America.

Strategic Considerations and Support for Reallocating Aid

Pursuant to the findings from these recent studies, our research begins with the assumption that donor publics are sensitive to geostrategic aspects of the aid-giving environment. Not only do citizens think about the political, commercial, and reputational consequences of providing aid to the developing world, they also think strategically about the consequences of withdrawing aid or shifting patterns of aid allocation. Hence, if alternative donors are likely to provide substitute aid flows in the event of aid reallocation, we expect a rational public to incorporate the impact of such substitution into their calculation of support for aid reallocation.

We also assume that individuals' attitudes toward foreign affairs are shaped by trust (Brewer and Steenbergen 2002; Brewer et al. 2004; in the realm of foreign aid, see Paxton and Knack 2012; Hirose et al. 2024).² Trust, or the belief that one will not be exploited by another, functions as a cognitive shortcut that reduces the perceived threat of ambiguous behavior particularly under conditions of uncertainty (Larson 1997; Brewer and Steenbergen 2002).³ When trust is high, actors may be more likely to perceive cooperation and goodwill; conversely, low trust may foster suspicion and increase the likelihood of interpreting even cooperative gestures as threatening.

While trust across nations can be fostered in a number of ways (e.g., through trade, investment, or cultural exchange), nothing more unambiguously institutionalizes mutual trust than the existence of a formal alliance.⁴ In the context of established alliances, citizens regard the presence of other countries' military units not as threatening but rather as enhancing security and thus benefitting their national interests. In the absence of a formal alliance, citizens are likely to oppose foreign military forces advancing or locating on their land: unable to trust the intentions of the other country, citizens would understand such actions as hostile and likely based on territorial ambitions.

In the aid-giving context as well, citizens may regard some alternative donors as more trustworthy than others. Thus, when the potential alternative supplier of aid is perceived as a trusted ally, we would expect less public resistance to reallocating aid from one recipient to another in a way that allows the substitute donor to replace the original country's aid flows. Reference to an ally as a potential substitute may even facilitate positive support for reallocation. When one donor reduces aid

to a particular region while an ally increases it—assuming that both share a common goal regarding that region’s development—the former is likely to trust that the latter will not exploit its increased influence at the former’s expense: such a substitution scenario could even represent strategically sensible burden-sharing. As a result, we expect that citizens in the aid-reducing country will be more likely to support aid reallocation when there is the possibility of aid substitution by an ally.⁵

In contrast, when the potential alternative supplier of aid is perceived as an adversary, we expect the country’s citizens to be anxious about providing that country the opportunity to increase its relative aid flows. Perceiving conflicts of interest between their country and the adversarial donor, citizens will expect the latter to exploit a situation in which their own government cedes space to the adversary. If citizens believe that foreign aid has strategic uses that are beneficial, they will expect the rival to secure these benefits at the expense of their own country.

These expectations are summarized in the following hypotheses:⁶

H1: Donor publics will be more likely to support reallocating aid when informed that a *foreign ally* is likely to replace their country’s aid relative to a scenario where there is no reference to a substitute donor.

H2: Donor publics will be less likely to support reallocating aid when informed that a *foreign adversary* is likely to replace their country’s aid relative to a scenario where there is no reference to a substitute donor.

Even where a trusted ally is a prospective substitute, however, there may be contextual variation in how members of the mass public think through the costs and benefits of aid reallocation. Specifically, within an alliance relationship, there might be more or less sensitivity to the aid substitution scenario depending on the relative power of the allies. In particular, there might be greater sensitivity on the part of the weaker side in the dyad to the powerful partner replacing aid activities within a specific sphere of influence.⁷ Substitution by an ally, in fact, risks some of the same threats as substitution by an adversary, such as loss of economic opportunities or prestige in the region. Therefore, when thinking about the weaker power in an allied dyad, we might see a less positive or even—in contrast to H1—a negative reaction among the public to the idea of aid substitution by an ally.

H3: The donor public in the weaker (stronger) side of an allied dyad will be more (less) sensitive about substitution by an ally when considering aid reallocation.⁸

Research Context

To test our hypotheses, we collected data in Japan between late March and early April 2023 and in the United States between September and October 2023. The Japan survey, implemented by Rakuten online, was designed to be nationally representative in terms of age, gender, and region (N=3,000); the U.S. survey, implemented online by YouGov, was designed to be nationally representative in terms of age, gender, social class, region, and level of education (N=6,095).⁹ In both surveys, the first half of the questionnaires solicited a range of opinions about international assistance, and the experiment that we study here was then embedded in the second half of the survey.

Historically, the United States has been the largest provider (by volume) of official development assistance (ODA) among the OECD-DAC countries, while Japan has been consistently one of the top five largest providers of ODA. However, citizens' attitudes toward foreign aid may diverge between these two donors, reflecting the fundamental difference in the countries' positions in the international system. Japanese citizens are well aware that their country is constitutionally banned from exercising non-defensive military options; thus, they attach more importance to foreign aid as a central tool of statecraft (Jain 2016; Kato 2016). On the other hand, while American citizens believe that the United States is less powerful today than in the period immediately after the collapse of the Soviet Union, large majorities continue to recognize their country as the world's leading military and economic power (Pew Research Center 2016), endowed with a variety of foreign policy tools, including proactive military options. Thus, in U.S. national discourse, foreign aid inevitably occupies a less prominent place.

This difference is revealed in our surveys. Table 1 compares the average score of respondents' opinions on five major questions regarding foreign aid in Japan and the United States. For four out of five questions, the average scores from the Japan survey are significantly more positive, suggesting that Japanese citizens attach more importance to foreign aid than their American counterparts.¹⁰ Overall, these differences in attitudes provide bases for our expectation that Japanese respondents will be more attentive than American respondents to aspects of the international environment when asked questions regarding foreign aid.

Table 1: Respondents' Opinions on Foreign Aid

	Respondents in Japan	Respondents in US	Difference
Aid should be increased	3.06 [3.02, 3.10] (2551)	2.88 [2.84, 2.91] (5328)	0.18*** [0.13, 0.23]
Aid is effective	5.09 [5.00, 5.18] (2607)	4.44 [4.36, 4.53] (5337)	0.64*** [0.52, 0.76]
Aid strengthens political influence in the world	3.28 [3.25, 3.31] (2645)	3.26 [3.23, 3.29] (5522)	0.02 [-0.03, 0.06]
Aid promotes national security	3.24 [3.21, 3.27] (2637)	3.09 [3.06, 3.12] (5458)	0.14*** [0.10, 0.18]
Aid is the morally right thing to do	3.16 [3.13, 3.19] (2711)	3.10 [3.07, 3.13] (5758)	0.06* [0.01, 0.10]

Note: “Aid should be increased” is a 5-point scale variable (1=decrease a great deal~3=stay the same~5=increase a great deal). “Aid is effective” is a 11-point scale variable (0=very ineffective~10=very effective). “Aid strengthens political influence,” “Aid promotes national security” and “Aid is the morally right thing to do” are 5-point scale variables (1=strongly disagree~3=neither agree nor disagree~5=strongly agree). All these questions were asked before assigning our treatments. 95% confidence intervals are in square brackets. The numbers of observations are in parentheses. *p<0.05; **p<0.01; ***p<0.001.

The United States and Japan also differ in terms of which set of countries their respective governments have (or have not) emphasized as targets of development assistance. Japan’s ODA was initially provided as part of war reparations to Asian countries after World War II, and it has consistently placed strategic priority on these countries, especially those in Southeast Asia. This strategic priority seems to be reflected in Japanese citizens’ attitudes as well.¹¹ Figure 1 compares the distribution of the outcome variable in the control condition (i.e., the condition that mentions neither China nor the United States) between the two regional reallocation scenarios in the Japan survey. While few respondents feel strongly about aid reallocation, there is obviously more support for reallocating aid from Africa to

Southeast Asia than there is for reallocating aid from Southeast Asia to Africa (mean of 2.6 versus mean of 2.4, $\delta = 0.2$, $p < 0.001$).

Figure 1: Distribution of the Outcome Variable in the Control Condition by Region for the Japan Survey

U.S. aid policy does not reveal as strong or as consistent a regional bias as that of Japan. However, our results also point to some variation in American citizens' support for aid reallocation by region. That is, Americans seem to place more priority on Latin America and less priority on Southeast Asia, as shown in Figure 2, which presents the U.S. version of the outcome variable distribution in the control condition based on various regional reallocation scenarios. The average levels of support for aid reallocation from Southeast Asia to Africa or Latin America, respectively, are around 2.5, whereas support for reallocation from Latin America to Africa and Southeast Asia, respectively, are 2.3 and 2.2.

Overall, these variations reaffirm the possibility that citizens may attach different levels of importance to different regions as appropriate targets of development assistance. As noted above, this possibility cannot be accounted for by the conventional scheme of simply asking the preferred amount of the total aid budget.

Figure 2: Distribution of the Outcome Variable in the Control Condition by Region for the U.S. Survey

Research Design

We provided our respondents hypothetical—yet as realistic as possible—descriptions of the contemporary aid-giving environment. Thus, in the Japan survey, we described that Japan currently provides aid to either Africa or Southeast Asia and informed respondents that Japan was considering reallocating aid from one region to the other. For the two treatment groups, we then specified a substitute donor that likely would increase aid flows to the former region in the event of Japan’s aid

reallocation; in a control condition, we made no reference to aid substitution. Concretely, the vignette read as follows for the treatment groups (while the last of the three paragraphs was omitted for the control group):

Over the last decade, Japan has provided a large amount of aid to {African, Southeast Asian} countries. This aid can help alleviate poverty and promote economic development in the countries that receive it, and it can promote Japan's trade and investment interests and Japan's national security.

Imagine that Japan is now considering reducing the amount of aid that it gives to {Africa, Southeast Asia} and giving this aid to {Southeast Asian, African} countries instead.

{In the event that Japan reduces its aid to {Africa, Southeast Asia}, it is quite likely that {China, the United States} will increase its aid to {Africa, Southeast Asia}.}

In sum, there were six treatment conditions for Japan: the two cross-regional specifications were crossed with the three patterns where (A) there was no mention of an alternative supplier of aid and where either (B) China or (C) the United States was presented as the alternative supplier of aid. In interpreting our results, we assume that Japanese citizens perceive the United States to be a friendly ally and China an adversarial rival. The alliance between Japan and the United States is, without question, one of the most solid bilateral alliances in the world (Allen and Sugg 2016). Japanese antipathy toward China, on the other hand, is known to be profound. In a 2019 survey of global attitudes toward China, 85 percent of Japanese survey respondents expressed an unfavorable view of China (Silver, Devlin, and Huang 2019).¹² In 2022 data, 74 percent of Japanese respondents said that they had a very or somewhat favorable opinion of the United States, while negative views of China remained at 85 percent.¹³

In the U.S. survey, as noted, we used Africa, Latin America, and Southeast Asia as relevant world regions. We retained China as the expected adversarial aid substitute and used both Japan and the United Kingdom to represent friendly/allied countries that might substitute for U.S. aid. The U.S. – U.K. relationship is frequently spoken of as a “special relationship” (Haugevik 2018). With regard to U.S. relations with Japan and China, we note that, aside from the recognized strength of the U.S.-Japan alliance mentioned above, survey data reveals that the average American has a far more positive view of Japan than China: on a 0-to-100 feeling thermometer, Americans, on average, rated Japan 33 degrees higher than China in 2021 data.¹⁴ In sum, for the U.S. survey, the total number of treatment conditions was 18: the three potential aid substitutes were crossed with six combinations of cross-regional reallocation scenarios.

Immediately after seeing the vignette, respondents were asked a series of four questions about potential mediating variables. In the Japan survey for example, we asked: “How do you think a reduction of aid to {Africa, Southeast Asia} would affect Japan’s ... (1) “economic interests (e.g. trade and investment opportunities)?”; (2) “national security interests (e.g. defense and regional stability)?”; (3) “international reputation?” and (4) “How do you think a reduction of aid to {Africa, Southeast Asia} would affect that region’s development prospects?” The answer options for these four mediating variables ranged on a 5-point scale from “damage greatly” (1) to “promote greatly” (5).

Finally, we asked our main outcome question, which reads (in the Japan survey): “Overall, to what extent do you agree or disagree that Japan should reduce its aid to {Africa, Southeast Asia} and give this aid to {Southeast Asian, African} countries instead?” The answer options for the outcome variable ranged on a 4-point scale from “strongly disagree” (1) to “strongly agree” (4). By focusing on preferences regarding reallocation of aid, we are able to ensure that responses are not contaminated by attitudes regarding the size of the total aid budget.

Regression Analysis

Our analysis starts by estimating the effects of the main treatments, i.e., the effects of possible aid substitutions by adversary and ally, respectively. Although our treatments are randomized, we use linear regression models with the following covariates to reduce the standard errors of the average treatment effects: (1) a binary variable for gender; (2) age; (3) seven (Japan) or eight (U.S.) indicators for location; (4) fifteen (Japan) or seventeen (U.S.) indicators for income; (5) seven (Japan) or five (U.S.) indicators for education level; and (6) measures of the subjective importance of maintaining relations with the regions from/to which aid is reallocated in the stimulus (1: not at all to 5: very important).¹⁵

Our main regression results for the Japan survey are illustrated in Figure 3 (see Table A3 in the Appendix for more details). We see roughly equal treatment effects in both the allied and adversarial substitute conditions. Furthermore, the results are very similar between the pooled analysis and the analyses conducted separately for the two region-specific scenarios.¹⁶

Figure 3. Average Treatment Effects in Japan Survey for Two Treatments. Coefficients from linear regression models, which include indicators for the two treatments and covariates described in the text, are shown. Error bars represent 95-percent confidence intervals calculated based on robust standard errors. The outcome variable—level of support for aid reallocation—is a 4-point scale variable (1=strongly disagree~4=strongly agree).

More specifically, when asked about reallocating aid from Africa to Southeast Asia, reference to the possibility that the United States will increase its aid to Africa leads to a statistically significant 0.09-unit reduction in support. Reference to China leads to a slightly larger fall in support (0.11 units), but the two treatment effects are not statistically distinguishable from each other ($p=0.56$). When asked about reallocating aid from Southeast Asia to Africa, the treatment effects are somewhat smaller in size—a 0.05-unit decrease when the United States is the alternative donor and a 0.09-unit decrease when China is mentioned. The treatment effect when the United States is used is not statistically distinguishable from zero at conventional levels, but the two treatment effects are indistinguishable from one another ($p=0.37$). For the pooled analysis, the treatment effect for the U.S. substitution condition is estimated to be a 0.08-unit reduction in the level of support for reallocation, and the treatment effect for the Chinese substitution condition is estimated to be a 0.12-unit reduction. Both these estimates are statistically significant but not distinguishable from each other ($p=0.20$). In the Japan data, therefore, we find support for H2 but evidence strongly disconfirming H1.

In Figure 4, we present the main results from the U.S. survey (see also Tables A4 and A5 in the Appendix). Depending on the regions referenced in the vignette, the point estimates may be either positive or negative for any of the three potential substitute donors, and they are never statistically significant. In the pooled analysis, substitution by Japan leads to a small increase in support for aid reallocation, whereas substitution by China leads to a small decrease in support for aid reallocation; as with the region-specific results, however, these treatment effects do not achieve traditional levels of statistical significance.¹⁷ In the U.S. data, therefore, we find evidence for neither H1 nor H2. Yet, this

does not mean there are no geostrategic elements in respondents' attitudes toward aid reallocation. In almost all cross-regional specifications, aid reallocation from region X to region Y is statistically significantly supported by those who believe region Y is important and region X is unimportant.¹⁸ Although American respondents do not respond to any substitution treatments, they do consider aid reallocation strategically.

Figure 4. Average Treatment Effects in U.S. Survey for Three Treatments. Coefficients from linear regression models, which include indicators for the three treatments and covariates described in the text, are shown. Error bars represent 95-percent confidence intervals calculated based on robust standard errors. The outcome variable—level of support for aid reallocation—is a 4-point scale variable.

That we see significant reactions to the stimuli in Japan but not in the United States supports H3: on average, American respondents react less strongly to the possibility that either an ally or an adversary will serve as a substitute donor than Japanese respondents. This is consistent with the notion that the stronger side in a donor dyad is less likely to be concerned about aid substitution than the weaker side. Where citizens deem foreign aid as relatively ineffective compared to other foreign policy tools, they will be less sensitive to competition—and less sensitive to coordination—in the foreign aid arena.

We admit, however, that we were surprised by the similar size of the negative reactions on the part of Japanese citizens to aid reallocation, regardless of whether the possible substitute donor is the United States or China. This evidence can be interpreted as indicative of the priority Japanese citizens place on using foreign aid as a strategic foreign policy tool. That is, Japanese citizens may be reluctant to forfeit their role as a prominent donor, even to the extent of disapproving the prospect that the United States—Japan's more powerful ally—may be willing to share the burden of providing aid. It is possible that Japanese citizens sense the fundamental difference in foreign policy goals between their own country and the United States, despite the strong bond of the bilateral alliance. This interpretation speaks to a topic of considerable debate in the literature of international relations over whether trust between states extends beyond the boundaries of specific areas of cooperation to take on a more general character (Downs and Jones 2002). Even allies who trust each other in the realm of security may not necessarily extend that trust across other domains—as in our case at hand, to the field of international development.

While we believe our results reflect geostrategic considerations on the part of donor publics, we are aware that a different line of interpretation is also possible, namely that references to alternate donors may cue donor publics to think about the humanitarian needs of citizens in aid-receiving countries. If so, and if donor publics think of aid primarily as development assistance to impoverished populations, they may be reluctant to withdraw aid regardless of the profile of the substitute donor. This interpretation cannot be dismissed easily, as it may be consistent with the pattern of treatment effects we observe for both countries. That is, Japanese respondents may on average oppose reallocation of aid because they recognize the profound needs in aid-receiving countries and tend to view aid as effective, while American respondents may generally be agnostic about aid reallocation because they tend to perceive aid as ineffective.

To distinguish between the alternative interpretations, we turn to mediation analysis of the mechanisms linking the treatments and respondents' preferences regarding aid reallocation. Although it is extremely difficult to specify all the potential reasons for respondents' reactions to various treatments, in the analysis below, we explore whether information regarding alternate donors activates geostrategic concerns and/or the development needs of aid-receiving countries among respondents.

Mediation Analysis

To conduct our mediation analysis, we utilize the set of questions which were asked in random order just prior to our main outcome question, namely how reallocation may affect the respondent country's (1) economic interests, (2) national security interests, and (3) international reputation and (4) the current recipient region's development prospects. Note that the first three focus on the donor country's geostrategic considerations, while the last is intended to capture concern about the aid-receiving region's need.

Figure 5: Effects of aid substitution on support for aid allocation mediated through four mechanisms. The vertical lines represent 95% confidence intervals with robust standard errors. The outcome variable—level of support for aid reallocation—is a 4-point scale variable. “Economic Interest,” “national security,” “international reputation,” and “development prospects” are 5-point scale mediating variables.

In Figure 5, we present the results after pooling all the cross-regional conditions for Japan and the United States respectively (see Tables A6 to A9 in the Appendix for the regression results which are the basis of our mediation analysis).¹⁹ In the Japan survey, we observe that the ally and adversary

treatments exhibit relatively similar mediation patterns. All the mediation effects are negative and estimated to be statistically distinguishable from zero, except for the one associated with the recipient region's development prospects under the U.S. substitution condition. The largest magnitude mediation effect is observed with the security mechanism in that Japanese respondents tend to disagree with aid reallocation because they think that the policy will negatively affect national security interests, and this effect is particularly strong when the possible substituting donor is identified as China. Overall, these results reveal the salience of strategic considerations, rather than humanitarian concerns, as the basis for Japanese citizens' attitudes toward aid reallocation.²⁰

An important caveat here is that our estimated mediation effects in the Japan survey, including the security-related one found to be significant, are relatively small compared to the unmodeled or direct effects of aid substitution on support for aid reallocation (see Figure 5 as well as Appendix Table A7). For instance, the direct effect of the U.S. treatment on the outcome variable in the pooled analysis is approximately five times larger than its indirect effect mediated through the security mechanism. Similarly, the direct effect of the China treatment is about four times larger than its indirect effect mediated through the security mechanism. The mediating effects we observe constitute only a portion of the total influence on respondents' attitudes arising from the expectation of aid substitution.

Turning to the results from the U.S. survey, the majority of the estimates for the hypothesized mediation pathways are not statistically significant.²¹ Given the contrast between the main findings from Japan and the United States that we reported earlier, this again points to a marked attitudinal difference between Japanese and American citizens regarding foreign aid reallocation. A further careful look at the results, however, reveals Americans are not entirely insensitive to geostrategic contexts. In the right panel of Figure 5, we see evidence that Americans distinguish the U.K. and Japan as friendly, and China as adversarial: according to our mediation analysis, it is only when China is referenced as the alternative donor that respondents in our U.S. survey think reallocation of their country's aid will negatively affect U.S. economic interests, national security interests, and international reputation, but it is noteworthy that ultimately, these effects are not substantial enough to generate statistically significant average treatment effects.

Discussion

We conducted experimental surveys in Japan and the United States in which respondents provided their opinions about aid reallocation and where subjects in the treatment conditions learned that either an ally or an adversary was likely to substitute for reallocated aid. In Japan, we find that

when confronted with information that an adversary (China) might provide funding in the event of aid reallocation, respondents reacted as expected (i.e., they decreased their support for aid reallocation), but also that the possibility of friendly substitution (by the United States) reduced support for aid reallocation. In light of the strong bond between the two countries, it is unlikely that we “misclassified” the United States as Japan’s ally. More likely is that, in Japan, the reference to substitution by another donor cues the idea of aid competition more generally—even when it is with a friendly donor—reminding people of the geostrategic purposes that foreign aid serves for the country and encouraging them to support the current use of foreign aid. Our descriptive statistics about attitudes toward aid support this interpretation, as we see more positive opinions about foreign aid among the Japanese sample relative to the American sample.

Turning to our U.S. survey results, while adversarial substitution activates respondents’ concerns about national security, economic interests, and international reputation, it does so to such a limited extent that we do not observe effects on the main outcome variable (i.e., support for aid reallocation). We also observe null effects in the case of friendly substitution. In the literature on public opinion in donor nations, a series of studies has recently shown that citizens update their attitudes regarding foreign aid in response to information about other international actors (Kohno et al. 2021; Wood, Hoy, and Pryke 2021; Chung, Pechenkina, and Skinner 2023). Our findings suggest that such updating occurs only sometimes, or perhaps only in some donor nations. In particular, the stark contrast in our results between the Japan and the U.S. surveys leads us to conclude that donor publics’ sensitivities toward the aid-giving environment are conditioned by their countries’ relative power positions. Since foreign aid is only one of several foreign policy tools that the country has at its disposal, it plays a less central role in the United States when it comes to pursuing national interests. Our results confirm a speculation expressed in one of the studies cited above, in which the authors note that “citizens of the United States ... may be less influenced by what other donors do. ... [T]he public in this superpower are less likely to feel that their security interests would be put at risk ... even if a potentially competitive donor country (such as China) is waiting in the wings” (Kohno et al. 2021).

We began our investigation, believing that citizens’ reactions to different prospects of aid substitution are shaped by whether they trust or distrust prospective substituting donors. Our findings, especially the contrast between the Japan and U.S. survey results, suggest that citizens engage in cost-benefit calculations that are more complex, perhaps even more strategic, than we initially expected. Distrust in substituting donors certainly augments citizens’ convictions not to reallocate aid, as shown clearly by Japanese data as well as in the United States case, albeit limitedly. Trust in substituting

donors, however, does not seem to be a sufficient condition for citizens to change their minds in support for reallocation. Our mediation analysis for the Japan survey indicates that the prospect of substitution by a trusted ally, the United States, activates security, economic and reputational concerns in almost the identical way as the prospect of substitution by China. A nuanced aspect of citizens' calculations is also revealed in our mediation analysis of the U.S. data, in which the prospect of substitutions by an ally, the United Kingdom or Japan, consistently yields greater effects across all mediating channels than the prospect of substitution by China, although the effects themselves are never significantly large.

Aside from incorporating the possibility of an ally (in addition to an adversary) serving as a substitute donor and conducting parallel surveys in countries with different relative power, we have sought, in this paper, to account for another important geostrategic concern that may affect donor publics' attitudes, namely cross-regional prioritization in foreign aid. Each donor nation, including Japan and the United States, is likely to place greater strategic priority on some countries rather than others when deciding how to allocate aid. Citizens themselves may also have their own individual preferences for a variety of reasons, including geographical proximity, cultural/ethnic connection, historical ties, as well as genuine humanitarian concerns. Our decision to focus on citizens' support for cross-regional reallocation of aid, rather than their preferred aid volume, has a methodological advantage: it reduces the influence of individuals' priors regarding the size of the aid budget and how government resources in general should be allocated, which they may consider in assessing the appropriate share of government spending on foreign aid. However, we are also aware of at least one disadvantage associated with our outcome variable. Specifying reallocation targets as regions may not be appropriate if respondents attach strategic importance to specific countries within regions. American citizens may, for example, attach exceptional importance to Israel in particular but not to the "Middle East" generally. While we have no a priori reason to believe this is a significant issue given the specific regions we chose, this is something to consider in future research.

Another noteworthy finding from our study is the consistent and substantial opposition to aid reallocation. In the control condition in the Japan survey, a majority of Japanese respondents expressed opposition to reallocating aid away from Southeast Asia, and a near majority opposed reallocating aid away from Africa. In the control condition in the United States, we also generally find preferences for the status quo (i.e., for not reallocating aid), although respondents are somewhat more likely to agree with the idea that aid can be reallocated away from Southeast Asia. These results of course beg a question: what, if anything, alters people's attitude toward aid reallocation more fundamentally?

National interest concerns—related to security, the economy, or international reputation—may not be subject to sudden changes; nor are the development prospects of aid-receiving countries likely to turn around overnight. In this context, how citizens in other countries react to the unprecedentedly radical change in U.S. aid policy under the second Trump administration, which has reduced overall aid provision around the world, certainly deserves special attention in future research.

Thinking about the constraints that public opinion puts on incumbent governments, our findings ultimately suggest that U.S. policy makers might have more flexibility in making decisions about how to deploy foreign aid than their Japanese counterparts. Whether this is good or bad depends on whether one's own views about how foreign aid should be used are in line with prevailing mass public opinion or not. The evidence in this paper suggests that the Japanese government might be constrained from reallocating aid in a way that is better for the pursuit of development but arguably worse for the pursuit of national interests, whereas the U.S. government, the largest provider of official development assistance in the world, has somewhat greater discretion to move foreign aid policy in a less self-interested direction, if leaders choose to do so.

Endnotes

¹ We collected our data and conducted our analyses before the dramatic reduction in U.S. foreign aid that occurred at the beginning of the second Trump administration.

² Comments from an anonymous reviewer helped us to develop the role of trust in the theoretical framework presented in this section. As these revisions took place after the data had been collected, we lack a measure of trust on the surveys used in the empirical section below.

³ The findings in international relations are an extension of more general findings in social psychology that trust affects how one interprets the motives and actions of other parties (e.g., Dirks and Ferrin 2001; Vlachos et al. 2009).

⁴ International relations scholars debate whether international institutions, such as alliances, foster trust (Keohane 1984; Ikenberry 2001) or else pre-existing trust gives rise to such institutions (Rathbun 2012).

⁵ As pointed out to us by an anonymous reviewer, some citizens might engage in a deeper analysis of what the consequences of aid substitution by an ally will be and might view such aid substitution as deleterious to national interests—perhaps economic interests in particular. This logic motivates H3 below, and we further return to this idea in the conclusion.

⁶ H1 and H2 were pre-registered, together with expectations expressed below as H3, in advance of analyzing the data collected in the United States in September and October 2023 but after the data collection in Japan in March 2023. We have included an anonymized version of the pre-registration in the appendix.

⁷ We can conceive strength and weakness within a dyad in terms of relative material capability, reputation for global leadership, and relative importance of the alliance in an overall alliance portfolio.

⁸ As noted above, H3 was not pre-registered. In the pre-registration document, the expectations underlying the hypothesis is stated specifically vis-à-vis a Japan / United States comparison: “In a comparison between how citizens in Japan feel about the United States acting as a substitute and how citizens in the United States feel about Japan acting as a substitute, we would expect more negative reactions in Japan.”

⁹ These surveys occurred as part of a bigger project with ongoing data collection. The sample sizes were determined by the funding available for that project.

¹⁰ The most noteworthy difference concerns responses to the question: “Overall, on a scale from 0 to 10, where 0 means ‘Very ineffective’ and 10 means ‘Very effective,’ how effective do you think government spending on overseas aid is?” As shown in Appendix Figure A1, in Japan, the average response is 5.09, with 5 being the mode of distribution, whereas in the United States the average is 4.44 with score 0 being the mode: as many as 18 percent of Americans believe that foreign aid is very ineffective.

¹¹ As described in Dafoe, Zhang, and Caughey (2018), survey respondents may not necessarily draw the intended inference from specific pieces of information in a vignette treatment. As pointed out by an anonymous reviewer, respondents might be cueing off of the perceived strategic importance of the regions, or they might be cueing off of other perceived characteristics of the countries in the named regions. See Baker (2015) for an example of how U.S. citizens cue off of specific country examples in the consideration of foreign aid.

¹² We note this figure is exceptionally high in comparison with the views toward China expressed in other allied countries. The corresponding figures for those in the United States, United Kingdom, Germany, and France ranged from 55 percent to 62 percent (Silver, Devlin, and Huang 2019).

¹³ Pew Research Center’s Global Attitudes & Trends Spring 2022 Survey Data, collected February 14 to June 3, 2022, available at <https://www.pewresearch.org/global/dataset/spring-2022-survey-data/> (accessed 16 January 2024).

¹⁴ Pew Research Center’s American Trends Panel Wave 82, collected from 1-7 February 2021, available at <https://www.pewresearch.org/global/dataset/american-trends-panel-wave-82/> (accessed 16 January 2024).

¹⁵ In Appendix Figures A2 and A3, as well as Appendix Tables A1 and A2, we report average treatment effect estimates without control variables. The results do not substantially differ from those obtained using regression models that include control variables.

¹⁶ Average treatment effect estimates for the Japan survey remain largely unchanged when the 4-point scale outcome variable is converted into a binary variable and analyzed using a probit model (see Figure A4 in the Appendix).

¹⁷ When the 4-point scale outcome variable is converted into a binary variable and analyzed using a probit model, the average treatment effect estimate of substitution by Japan on support for aid reallocation from Africa to Latin America is significantly positive. Apart from this difference, average treatment effect estimates for the U.S. survey remain largely unchanged (see Figure A5 in the Appendix).

¹⁸ The same pattern can also be seen in the Japan survey (see Table A3 in the Appendix).

¹⁹ Mediation effect estimates for both the Japan and the U.S. surveys remain largely unchanged when the 4-point scale outcome variable is converted into a binary variable and analyzed using a probit model (see Figure A6 in the Appendix).

²⁰ While our treatments are randomized, the mediators are not. Mediation effects would be biased if unobserved confounders for the mediators exist. Appendix Figure A7 illustrates the sensitivity or robustness of our significant mediation effects to hypothesized unobserved confounders in the Japan survey. Although the security mechanism exhibits the largest mediation effect, it does not substantially differ from the other two significant mechanisms – the economic and reputation mechanisms – in terms of sensitivity or robustness to unobserved confounders.

²¹ In contrast to the Japan survey, the unmodeled or direct effects in the U.S. survey are statistically insignificant (see Table A9 in the Appendix).

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